

Cannabis use in adolescence: physical and functional repercussions

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ABSTRACT Adolescence is a period of great physical, emotional and social transformations that aims to make the individual a mature and reproducible being. During this phase of life, adolescents are subject to many external influences and risky behaviours that can cause permanent changes, including illicit drug use. Cannabis use has been increasing worldwide, and a growing number of adolescents have been exposed to this drug. This article presents some characteristics of adolescent neurological development and the physical and physiological repercussions that can be caused by cannabis use.

KEYWORDS Adolescence, Cannabis, Drugs, Adolescent behaviour, Cannabinoids

Introduction

Adolescence is a critical stage in human development characterised by substantial changes in physical, psychological and social domains, that includes the ability to perform complex cognitive tasks and regulate affect and behaviour due to, among other structures, the hyperactive limbic system involved in motivation, affective learning and reward, in order to achieve long-term goals [1,2]. In this phase of life, characterized by great neuron maturation, it is observed increases in affective reactivity, peer-directed social interactions, risk-taking and sensation-seeking [3].

Cannabis has been used throughout the world for millennia and is the most commonly preferred illicit drug by adolescents, with typical ages of onset ranging between 16 and 19 years. The growing trend of prodrug websites and the online vending shops may contribute to the increasing trend of consumption, and the high rates of adolescent cannabis use concern because they are particularly vulnerable to the effects on brain structure and function [4-6]. Disruptions in brain development related to neurotoxic effects of regular marijuana use could significantly alter neurodevelopmental trajectories by not only

changing neurochemical communication and genetic expression of neural development but causing a toxic effect on brain tissue. Such a marijuana-related effect on white matter and grey matter structures could have widespread implications for healthy brain development from childhood to young adulthood on subtle cognitive functioning and success in daily functioning [7,8].

Worldwide several regions are legalising medicinal and recreational use making cannabis more available. Newer, numerous synthetic cannabinoids have been detected, some of which are even more potent than delta-9 tetrahydrocannabinol itself on the cannabinoid receptors [9,10], novel products and devices used to administer are created, and the perception of harmfulness is not yet adequately understood by users [11], making teens more susceptible to deleterious effects [12].

To better understand the deleterious effects of cannabis on the body, it is necessary to highlight some aspects of the development and physiology of the adolescent central nervous system (CNS).

The central nervous system of the adolescent

The development of the human brain is a differentiated and complex process that goes from the molecular events of gene expression to its maximum maturity and interaction with the environment, being subject to nutritional influences and harms caused by various substances [13]. A lot of evidence morphological, pharmacological, neurochemical and neurobehavioral suggests that the brain remains in construction during the second and third decades of life [14,15]. Adolescence presents a window of plasticity in the CNS because it is a critical period of

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Table 1 Anatomical changes due to cannabis use.

Smaller whole brain (reduced cortical surface and thickness)
Reduced white matter volume and integrity
Reduced grey matter volume especially in brain regions with high cannabinoids receptors (hippocampus, prefrontal cortex, amygdala, cerebellum)
[1,7,13,19,20,22,41-44]

Table 2 Functional changes due to cannabis use.

Reduced: learning; attention and memory performance; motivation; psychomotor speed and executive functions; impaired reaction times; affective and reward processing; intelligence quotient;
Poorer: performance on tests of processing speed; impulse control;
Hallucinations; symptoms of schizophrenia-like psychotic disorders; increased risk of psychosis
sleep impairment (altered sleep architecture, reduced rapid eye movement sleep, difficulty with sleep initiation and maintenance, "strange dreams",
[1,7,8,10,19,20,22,28,39,41-43,45-49]

neurodevelopment and quite sensitive to environmental factors during which synaptic modulation and myelination are highly active and could be disrupted by exogenous exposures to drugs and toxins [16-18].

A large body of literature has shown dynamic changes in CNS structures that are ongoing over adolescent development. For instance, dendritic pruning and elimination of synapses likely results in cortical thinning and decreased cerebral to some degree, whereas some subcortical structures such as the hippocampus and amygdala have been shown to increase with age [7,11,19]. The white matter that is composed of myelin-coated axons are concentrated in the inner brain and facilitates communication between regions to create cortico-cortical and cortico-subcortical networks [20].

One brain region that develops substantially during adolescence is the prefrontal cortex, which is involved in executive functions, such as decision making, inhibitory control, and planning. In the prefrontal cortex, grey matter (consisting of neuronal cell bodies, dendrites, synapses, and unmyelinated axons) increases in adolescence, and the loss is thought to be due to synaptic pruning that sculpts neuronal circuitry according to the environment during sensitive periods of brain development [21,22]. Prefrontal, parietal and temporal brain regions are particularly vulnerable to the adverse effects of cannabis because they have a high density of cannabinoid receptors, undergo neuroanatomical changes during neurodevelopment such as interference in synaptic connectivity and plasticity [4,23].

The Endocannabinoid System

Just over thirty years ago, a system of receptors that are stimulated by naturally occurring substances, called endocannabinoids, has been identified in various organs of the human body. This so-called "Endocannabinoid System" (ES) is a lipid neuro-modulatory system made up of endogenous receptors and ligands, responsible for several controls related to the regulation of many essential functions such as movement, memory, emotions, sleep and appetite. Such receptors are located throughout the body, embedded in cell membranes, where they perform multiple internal functions and mediate the relationship between the

individual and the external environment [24-26].

Endocannabinoids are naturally occurring arachidonic acid metabolites, and include anandamide and 2-arachidonoylglycerol (2-AG). Neurons synthesize these substances following membrane depolarization and travel into the synaptic cleft, where they bind to CB1 receptors on presynaptic terminals [27]. The two primary cannabinoid receptors are "cannabinoid subtype-1" (CB1, that is found at high concentrations in some brain regions associated with reward, cognitive processing and emotions, amygdala, cerebellum, hippocampus, basal ganglia and thalamus) [9], and "cannabinoid subtype-2" (CB2) that is found mainly in the immune system and intestine [22,28]. Cannabinoid receptors modulate the secretion of gamma-aminobutyric acid and glutamate within the CNS, two neurotransmitters that have significant neurodevelopmental effects on the brains [29].

During adolescence, changes occur indicating that this system is involved in the maturation of the CNS and that activation by exogenous THC may dysregulate this maturation, either directly or through indirect regulation processes resulting in inhibition of the CB1 receptor signalling [22].

Cannabis

The cannabis, a plant originated in Central Asia and currently growing worldwide, contains more than 500 active herbal compounds and can be consumed in several forms: inhaled (most common), ingested (gummy bears or chocolate squares) or applied topically on the oral, rectal or vaginal mucosae [10,30]. Route of administration affects the onset, intensity and duration of drug effects and adverse health outcomes [31], as well as the earlier age of onset, the greater the deleterious effects on the body [32-33]. Phytocannabinoids are compounds found in the Cannabis sativa plant, and the primary psychoactive substance is delta-9 tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) whose concentration varies in the different strains of cannabis (6% to 20%), is rapidly absorbed by the lungs, binds to lipoproteins, is stored in adipose tissue and excreted at a low rate, distributed systemically by perfusion and easily crosses the blood-brain barrier within seconds to minutes of use, remaining in the body for long

periods (5,18). The bioavailability varies among individuals according to number, duration, spacing of puffs and inhalation volume, and is metabolised through the liver [34,35].

The effects of THC are due to its action on cannabinoid receptor type 1 (CB1) in the CNS (areas associated with cognition, memory, pain and motor co-ordination) [22]. Cannabis use disrupts critical brain changes that occur in adolescence, including myelination, synaptic pruning, and maturation of the endogenous cannabinoid system, making the users susceptible to structural and functional brain alterations [6].

Medicinal use

Evidence of cannabis use from a scientific perspective began in the nineteenth century with attempts for the treatment of rheumatic pain and infantile seizures [36]. Currently, discussions about the effects of cannabis have been more frequent in both scientific and media circles. In recent years several potential therapies to treat various clinical symptoms have been attributed to cannabis due to its pharmacological properties such as: antiepileptic, analgesia in neuropathic and chronic pain, antiemetic in cancer disease and therapy, antispastic in stroke and multiple sclerosis; appetite stimulation, and in treatment of intraocular pressure associated with glaucoma [2,37-40]. Therefore, it is necessary to highlight that some clinical indications still need further studies to verify the risks and benefits, in addition to specific clinical indications and strict medical follow-up.

Neuropharmacology and anatomic consequences of cannabis use

Several studies have utilised functional magnetic resonance imaging methods to identify patterns of brain changes that are specific to cannabis use in adolescence [19]. These studies have demonstrated, among other findings, increased neural activity, that is, the brain needs to compensate for altered integrity caused by cannabis use.

The primary anatomical (table 1) and functional (table 2) alterations that can be verified in the CNS of the adolescent are:

Conclusions

Cannabis use by adolescents has been associated with medical, cognitive and psychological sequelae, as psychosocial indices of disadvantage, social marginalization, criminal behaviours, and high risk of mortality [7,19,41]. Meanwhile, it seems to be increasingly accepted as a safe recreational drug it is important to understand better what are the implications of use and potential interactions with other substances during critical periods of development such as adolescence [41,47,50]. Neurotoxic effects of cannabis on the CNS demonstrate the importance of prevention and policy efforts targeting adolescent use [42,51]. Therefore, it is necessary to remember that the consumption development sequence begins with a legalized drug and rapidly evolves into other substances with a higher potential of abuse [5,18].

Broad education and prevention campaigns are urgent. Education about cannabis use should be age-specific and start in elementary education and continue through high school [52-54] including more precise messages of the neurobiological and environmental risk factors that contribute to health-related outcomes among adolescent cannabis users. Because cannabis use is associated with neuroanatomic and functional changes in various brain regions, especially in the basic structures that integrate

the motivation, learning and reward circuits, essential for adolescent education and maturation, the knowledge of all these problems caused by cannabis use makes everyone responsible for the actions needed to promote adolescent health.

Conflict of Interest

None

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